

A Diagrammatic Algebra for Program Logics

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Abstract. Tape diagrams provide a convenient graphical notation for arrows of rig categories, i.e., categories equipped with two monoidal products, \oplus and \otimes . In this work, we introduce Kleene-Cartesian rig categories, namely rig categories where \otimes provides a Cartesian bicategory, while \oplus a Kleene bicategory. We show that the associated tape diagrams can conveniently deal with Hoare logic.

Keywords: Rig categories · Cartesian Bicategories · Program logics.

1 Introduction

The calculus of relations, originally introduced by De Morgan and Peirce in the late 19th century, is an ancestor of first order logic that has been revitalised by Tarski in 1941. With the dawn of program logics, the calculus of relations – extended with transitive closure – was early recognised [53] to play a key role.

Around the same time, Lawvere was pioneering categorical logic by introducing the concept of *functorial semantics* [47]. Given an algebraic theory T (in the sense of universal algebra, i.e., a signature Σ and a set of equations E), one can freely generate a Cartesian category \mathcal{L}_T . Models, in the standard algebraic sense, correspond one-to-one with Cartesian functors F from \mathcal{L}_T to **Set**, the category of sets and functions. More generally, models of the theory in any Cartesian category \mathbf{C} are represented by Cartesian functors $F : \mathcal{L}_T \rightarrow \mathbf{C}$. However this approach fails if one tries to apply it to relational theories by choosing \mathbf{C} as **Rel**, the category of sets and relations, because the Cartesian product of sets is not the categorical product in **Rel**.

A refinement of Lawvere’s method for relational structures has been recently proposed in [13,15,26]. Starting from a *monoidal signature*, one can freely generate a *Cartesian bicategory* [40] and define models as morphisms into $(\mathbf{Rel}, \otimes, 1)$, the monoidal category of relations, where the monoidal product \otimes is the Cartesian product of sets. This framework captures regular theories, i.e., those involving the $\{\exists, \wedge, \top\}$ -fragment of first order logic. More recently [10], this approach was extended to full first order logic by deriving negation from the interaction of Cartesian and linear bicategories [21].

In this paper, we extend the Cartesian bicategory framework in a different direction: program logics. In the last decades, there has been an explosion of program logics and many researchers felt the need for more systematic approaches. Our proposal is based on relational and categorical algebra. We propose tape diagrams as an “assembly language” for interpreting various program logics (Remark 3). While the inference rules

for each of these logics are usually defined by the ingenuity of the researchers, in our approach such rules follow from the laws of Kleene-Cartesian rig categories. These laws arise from the interaction of canonical categorical structures on the category of sets and relations. Crucially, the same approach has led to identify various categorical structures corresponding to various well-known logics (Figure 1).

	Logic	Categorical structure
[47]	Equational logic	Cartesian category
[15]	Regular logic	Cartesian bicategory
[11]	Coherent logic	Finite-biproduct Cartesian bicategory
[10]	First-order logic	First-order bicategory
This work	Program logic	Kleene-Cartesian rig category

Fig. 1: Categorical structures correspond to logics.

An idea, originating at least from Bainbridge [4], is to model data flow using the Cartesian product of relations, $(\mathbf{Rel}, \otimes, 1)$, and control flow using a different monoidal structure on relations: $(\mathbf{Rel}, \oplus, 0)$. In this second structure, the monoidal product \oplus is the disjoint union of sets, which acts both as a coproduct and a product, hence, a *biproduct*. Both monoidal categories are *traced* [39]: the trace in $(\mathbf{Rel}, \otimes, 1)$ represents feedback, while in $(\mathbf{Rel}, \oplus, 0)$ –the focus of our work– it provides *iteration* [54].

Our first step is to extract from $(\mathbf{Rel}, \oplus, 0)$ the categorical structures essential for modelling control flow, which we term *Kleene bicategories*. Essentially, a Kleene bicategory is a poset-enriched traced monoidal category where the monoidal product \oplus is a biproduct, and the induced natural comonoid [27] is *right adjoint* to the natural monoid. The trace must satisfy a posetal variant of the so-called *uniformity* condition [20,33]. The term “Kleene” is justified because every Kleene bicategory forms a (typed) Kleene algebra in Kozen’s sense [41,43] (Corollary 1), while any Kleene algebra canonically gives rise, through the biproduct completion [48], to a Kleene bicategory.

To model control and data flow within a unified categorical structure, we employ *rig categories* [46], categories equipped with two monoidal products, \oplus and \otimes , where \otimes distributes over \oplus . We define *Kleene-Cartesian rig (kc rig) categories*, where \oplus and \otimes exhibit the structures of Kleene and Cartesian bicategories, respectively. To construct the freely generated kc rig category (Theorem 2), we extend *tape diagrams* [11], a diagrammatic notation recently introduced for rig categories. Intuitively, tape diagrams are *string diagrams* [38] in which other string diagrams are nested: the inner diagrams model data flow, and the outer ones model control flow. On one hand, this offers an intuitive unified picture of Bainbridge’s idea; on the other it allows for visualising the laws of kc rig categories (Figures 2, 3 and 4) in a way that enlightens several monoidal algebras occurring in different types of systems [56,22,3,28,18,36,16,12,14,51,29].

We then introduce *Kleene-Cartesian theories* and their models that, like in Lawvere’s approach, coincide with functors (Proposition 3). We illustrate an example of a Kleene-Cartesian theory which is not first order: Peano’s axiomatisation of natural numbers. We demonstrate how imperative programs and their logics [35,44,24,50,2] – even more sophisticated ones, like [7], where the interaction of data and control flow play a key role – can be encoded within Kleene-Cartesian tape diagrams. In particular, we show that the rules of Hoare logic follow from the laws of kc rig categories (Propo-

sition 4). Finally, the framework is expressive enough to capture the positive fragment of the calculus of relations with transitive closure, which is the departure of our journey.

The full version of the paper is found in [9] which contains the missing proofs.

2 The calculus of relations

We commence by recalling the positive fragment of the calculus of relations with reflexive and transitive closure (CR). Its syntax is given

by the grammar on the left, where R is taken from a given set Σ of generating symbols. Beyond the usual relational

$$E ::= R \mid id \mid E; E \mid \quad (1)$$

composition $;$, union \cup , intersection \cap and their units id ,

$$E^\dagger \mid \top \mid E \cap E \mid \quad (2)$$

\perp and \top , the calculus features two unary operations:

$$E^* \mid \perp \mid E \cup E \quad (3)$$

the opposite $(\cdot)^\dagger$ and the reflexive and transitive closure $(\cdot)^*$. Composition and identities are defined, for sets X, Y, Z , and relations $R \subseteq X \times Y$, $S \subseteq Y \times Z$, as

$$R; S \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{(x, z) \mid \exists y. y \in Y. (x, y) \in R \wedge (y, z) \in S\} \quad \text{and} \quad id_X \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{(x, x) \mid x \in X\},$$

the opposite as $R^\dagger \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{(y, x) \mid (x, y) \in R\}$, while for $R \subseteq X \times X$, its reflexive and transitive closure is $R^* \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} R^n$ where $R^0 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} id_X$ and $R^{n+1} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} R; R^n$.

Its semantics, illustrated below, is defined wrt a *relational interpretation* I , that is, a set X together with a binary relation $\rho(R) \subseteq X \times X$ for each $R \in \Sigma$.

$$\begin{aligned} \langle R \rangle_I &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \rho(R) & \langle id \rangle_I &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} id_X & \langle E_1; E_2 \rangle_I &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \langle E_1 \rangle_I; \langle E_2 \rangle_I \\ \langle E^\dagger \rangle_I &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \langle E \rangle_I^\dagger & \langle \perp \rangle_I &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{\} & \langle E_1 \cup E_2 \rangle_I &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \langle E_1 \rangle_I \cup \langle E_2 \rangle_I \\ \langle E^* \rangle_I &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \langle E \rangle_I^* & \langle \top \rangle_I &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} X \times X & \langle E_1 \cap E_2 \rangle_I &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \langle E_1 \rangle_I \cap \langle E_2 \rangle_I \end{aligned}$$

Two expressions E_1, E_2 are said to be *equivalent*, written $E_1 \equiv_{\text{CR}} E_2$, iff $\langle E_1 \rangle_I = \langle E_2 \rangle_I$ for all interpretations I . For instance, $(R^*)^\dagger \equiv_{\text{CR}} (R^\dagger)^*$. Inclusion, denoted by \leq_{CR} , is defined analogously by replacing $=$ with \subseteq . Axiomatisations and decidability of \equiv_{CR} have been studied focusing on several different fragments: see [52] and the references therein. Particularly interesting are the *allegorical fragment*, consisting of (1) and (2), and the *Kleene fragment* consisting of (1) and (3).

Our starting observation is that these two fragments arise from two different traced monoidal structures on **Rel**, the category of sets and relations: $(\mathbf{Rel}, \otimes, 1)$ and $(\mathbf{Rel}, \oplus, 0)$. In the former, the monoidal product \otimes is given by the cartesian product of sets and, for relations $R: X_1 \rightarrow Y_1, S: X_2 \rightarrow Y_2$, $R \otimes S: X_1 \otimes X_2 \rightarrow Y_1 \otimes Y_2$ is defined as

$$R \otimes S \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{((x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2)) \mid (x_1, y_1) \in R \text{ and } (x_2, y_2) \in S\} \text{ with unit } 1 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{\bullet\}.$$

In $(\mathbf{Rel}, \oplus, 0)$, $0 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{\}$, \oplus on sets is their disjoint union and $R \oplus S: X_1 \oplus X_2 \rightarrow Y_1 \oplus Y_2$ is

$$R \oplus S \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{((x_1, 1), (y_1, 1)) \mid (x_1, y_1) \in R\} \cup \{((x_2, 2), (y_2, 2)) \mid (x_2, y_2) \in S\}.$$

Here, we tag with 1 and 2 the elements of the disjoint union of two arbitrary sets.

For all sets X , the unique function $!_X: X \rightarrow 1$ and the pairing $\langle id_X, id_X \rangle \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \blacktriangleleft_X: X \rightarrow X \otimes X$ form a comonoid in $(\mathbf{Rel}, \otimes, 1)$. Similarly the unique function $\uparrow_X: 0 \rightarrow X$ and the

$(f \sqcap g) \sqcap h = f \sqcap (g \sqcap h)$	$f \sqcap g = g \sqcap f$	$f \sqcap \top = f$	$f \sqcap f = f$
$(f \sqcap g); h \leq (f; h \sqcap g; h)$	$h; (f \sqcap g) \leq (h; f \sqcap h; g)$	$f; \top \leq \top \geq \top; f$	
$(f; g)^\dagger = g^\dagger; f^\dagger$	$(f \otimes g)^\dagger = f^\dagger \otimes g^\dagger$	$(id_X)^\dagger = id_X$	$(f^\dagger)^\dagger = f$

Table 1: Derived laws in Cartesian bicategories.

for all objects X, Y and arrows $f, g: X \rightarrow Y$. The reader can easily check that, in **Rel**, these correspond to the intersection $f \sqcap g$, the top relation $X \times Y$ and the opposite relation f^\dagger , respectively. From now on, we will depict a morphism $f: X \rightarrow Y$ as $x \text{---} \boxed{f} \text{---} y$, and use $y \text{---} \boxed{f} \text{---} x$ as syntactic sugar for f^\dagger .

Proposition 1. *In any Cartesian bicategory, the laws in Table 1 hold.*

An arrow $f: X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be *single valued* iff satisfies (SV) below, *total* iff satisfies (TOT), *injective* iff satisfies (INJ) and *surjective* iff satisfies (SUR).

$x \text{---} \boxed{f} \text{---} y \leq x \text{---} \boxed{f} \text{---} y$	(SV)	$y \text{---} \boxed{f} \text{---} y \leq y \text{---} y$	(6)
$x \text{---} \bullet \leq x \text{---} \boxed{f} \text{---} \bullet$	(TOT)	$x \text{---} x \leq x \text{---} \boxed{f} \text{---} \boxed{f} \text{---} x$	(7)
$\begin{matrix} x \\ x \end{matrix} \text{---} \boxed{f} \text{---} y \leq \begin{matrix} x \\ x \end{matrix} \text{---} \boxed{f} \text{---} y$	(INJ)	$x \text{---} \boxed{f} \text{---} \boxed{f} \text{---} x \leq x \text{---} x$	(8)
$\bullet \text{---} y \leq \bullet \text{---} \boxed{f} \text{---} y$	(SUR)	$y \text{---} y \leq y \text{---} \boxed{f} \text{---} \boxed{f} \text{---} y$	(9)

Lemma 1. *In a Cartesian bicategory, an arrow $f: X \rightarrow Y$ is single valued iff (6), it is total iff (7), it is injective iff (8) and it is surjective iff (9).*

Any Cartesian bicategory is self-dual compact closed and thus *traced*. Later on, to deal with *tests* in imperative programs we will use *coreflexives*, namely arrows $f: X \rightarrow X$ such that $f \leq id_X$. In Cartesian bicategories, they enjoy several useful properties:

Lemma 2. *In a Cartesian bicategory, the following hold:*

1. f is a coreflexive iff f is transitive ($f; f \leq f$), symmetric ($f^\dagger \leq f$) and single valued.
2. Coreflexives $X \rightarrow X$ are in bijective correspondence with arrows $1 \rightarrow X$.
3. For all coreflexives $f, g: X \rightarrow X$, $f; g = f \sqcap g$; Moreover, for $f': 1 \rightarrow X$ corresponding to f and $i: 1 \rightarrow X$, $i \sqcap f' = i; f$.

4 Kleene Bicategories

Now, we introduce Kleene bicategories and show that their laws capture the complete axiomatisation of Kleene algebras from [41]. Recall that a category \mathbf{C} is *enriched over join-semilattices* if every homset carries a join \sqcup semilattice with bottom \perp and composition ; distributes over it (see (10) and (11) in Table 2). A (typed) *Kleene algebra* [41,43] is a category enriched over join-semilattices equipped with a *Kleene star operator*, namely a family of operations $(\cdot)^*: \mathbf{C}[X, X] \rightarrow \mathbf{C}[X, X]$ such that for all $f: X \rightarrow X$, $r: X \rightarrow Y$ and $l: Y \rightarrow X$ the four laws in (12) hold.

$(f \sqcup g) \sqcup h = f \sqcup (g \sqcup h)$	$f \sqcup g = g \sqcup f$	$f \sqcup \perp = f$	$f \sqcup f = f$	(10)
$(f \sqcup g); h = (f; h \sqcup g; h)$	$h; (f \sqcup g) = (h; f \sqcup h; g)$	(11)		
$id_X \sqcup f; f^* \leq f^*$	$id_X \sqcup f^*; f \leq f^*$	$f; r \leq r \implies f^*; r \leq r$	$l; f \leq l \implies l; f^* \leq l$	(12)

Table 2: Axioms of (Typed) Kleene Algebras

Definition 2. A finite biproduct (shortly, *fb*) category with idempotent convolution is a poset enriched symmetric monoidal category $(\mathbf{C}, \oplus, 0)$ and, for every object X in \mathbf{C} , a monoid $(\triangleright_X, \uparrow_X)$ and a comonoid $(\triangleleft_X, \downarrow_X)$ satisfying the usual coherence conditions s.t.:

1. $(\triangleleft_X, \downarrow_X)$ is right adjoint to $(\triangleright_X, \uparrow_X)$;
2. arrows $f: X \rightarrow Y$ are both monoid and comonoid morphisms: $f; \triangleleft_Y = \triangleleft_X; (f \oplus f)$, $f; \downarrow_Y = \downarrow_X; \triangleright_Y; f = (f \oplus f); \triangleright_X$ and $\uparrow_X; f = \uparrow_Y$.

Remark 1. A finite biproduct category is defined as above but without the poset enrichment and the adjointness condition: 0 is both final and initial object and \oplus is both a categorical product and coproduct, i.e., a biproduct [27]. While any finite biproduct category is enriched over commutative monoids, the additional conditions in Definition 2 guarantee that this is enriched over join semilattices where \sqcup and \perp are defined for all objects X, Y and arrows $f, g: X \rightarrow Y$ as on the left below.

$$f \sqcup g \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} x \rightarrow \begin{array}{c} \boxed{f} \\ \boxed{g} \end{array} \rightarrow y \quad \perp \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} x \rightarrow \bullet \leftarrow y \quad f^* \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} x \rightarrow \begin{array}{c} \boxed{f} \\ \bullet \end{array} \rightarrow x \quad (13)$$

The reader can easily check that $(\mathbf{Rel}, \oplus, 0)$ with $\triangleleft_X, \downarrow_X, \triangleright_X, \uparrow_X$ defined as in (4) is a finite biproduct category with idempotent convolution and that \sqcup and \perp give union and empty relation. Unfortunately, finite biproduct categories with idempotent convolution do not have enough structure to deal with $(\cdot)^*$: differently from Cartesian bicategories they are not necessarily traced. Such structure has to be explicitly added:

Definition 3. A Kleene bicategory \mathbf{C} is both a finite biproduct category with idempotent convolution and a poset enriched traced monoidal category such that

1. for all objects X , the trace tr_X satisfies the axiom $\text{tr}_X(\triangleright_X; \triangleleft_X) \leq id_X$;
2. the trace is posetal uniform: for all $f: S \oplus X \rightarrow S \oplus Y$ and $g: T \oplus X \rightarrow T \oplus Y$,
 - (AU1) if $\exists r: S \rightarrow T$ such that $f; (r \oplus id_Y) \leq (r \oplus id_X); g$, then $\text{tr}_S f \leq \text{tr}_S g$;
 - (AU2) if $\exists r: T \rightarrow S$ such that $(r \oplus id_X); f \leq g; (r \oplus id_Y)$, then $\text{tr}_S f \leq \text{tr}_S g$.

A morphism of Kleene bicategory is a poset enriched symmetric monoidal functor preserving monoids, comonoids and traces.

The laws in (AU1) and (AU2) are the posetal extension of the uniformity condition for traces (see e.g. [33]). To the best of our knowledge, they have never been studied. Instead, the axioms in 1 already appeared in the literature (see e.g. [51]). Like in any finite biproduct category with trace (see e.g. [20]), in a Kleene bicategory one can define for each endomorphism $f: X \rightarrow X$, a morphism $f^*: X \rightarrow X$ as in (13). The distinguishing property of Kleene bicategories is that $(\cdot)^*$ is a Kleene star operator: see (12). Viceversa, any Kleene star operation gives rise to a trace satisfying the laws of Kleene bicategories.

Theorem 1. *Let \mathbf{C} be a fb category with idempotent convolution. \mathbf{C} is a Kleene bicategory iff \mathbf{C} has a Kleene-star operator.*

Corollary 1. *All Kleene bicategories are typed Kleene algebras.*

The opposite does not hold: not all Kleene algebras are monoidal categories. Nevertheless, from a Kleene algebra, one can canonically build a Kleene bicategory by means of the *matrix construction*, aka *biproduct completion* [23,48]. See [9, Sec. 6.3]

5 Rig Categories

We have seen that **Rel** carries two monoidal categories $(\mathbf{Rel}, \otimes, 1)$ and $(\mathbf{Rel}, \oplus, 0)$. The appropriate setting for studying their interaction is given by rig categories [46,37].

Definition 4. *A rig category is a category \mathbf{C} with two symmetric monoidal structures $(\mathbf{C}, \otimes, 1)$ and $(\mathbf{C}, \oplus, 0)$ and natural isomorphisms*

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{X,Y,Z}^l: X \otimes (Y \oplus Z) &\rightarrow (X \otimes Y) \oplus (X \otimes Z) & \lambda_X^\bullet: 0 \otimes X &\rightarrow 0 \\ \delta_{X,Y,Z}^r: (X \oplus Y) \otimes Z &\rightarrow (X \otimes Z) \oplus (Y \otimes Z) & \rho_X^\bullet: X \otimes 0 &\rightarrow 0 \end{aligned}$$

satisfying certain coherence axioms [46]. A rig category is said to be right strict when $\lambda^\bullet, \rho^\bullet$ and δ^r are all identity natural isomorphisms. A right strict rig functor is a strict symmetric monoidal functor for both \otimes and \oplus preserving δ^l .

A sesquistrict rig category is a functor $H: \mathbf{S} \rightarrow \mathbf{C}$, where \mathbf{S} is a discrete category and \mathbf{C} is a right strict rig category, such that for all $A \in \mathbf{S}$

$$\delta_{H(A),X,Y}^l: H(A) \otimes (X \oplus Y) \rightarrow (H(A) \otimes X) \oplus (H(A) \otimes Y)$$

is an identity morphism. Given $H: \mathbf{S} \rightarrow \mathbf{C}$ and $H': \mathbf{S}' \rightarrow \mathbf{C}'$ two sesquistrict rig categories, a sesquistrict rig functor from H to H' is a pair $(\alpha: \mathbf{S} \rightarrow \mathbf{S}', \beta: \mathbf{C} \rightarrow \mathbf{C}')$, with α a functor and β a strict rig functor, such that $\alpha; H' = H; \beta$.

Intuitively, a sesquistrict rig category is right strict and, partially (just for the selected class of objects \mathbf{S}), left strict. For more details, we refer the reader to [11, Sec. 4].

From any rig category \mathbf{C} , one can construct its (right) strictification $\bar{\mathbf{C}}$ [37] and then embed $ob(\mathbf{C})$, the discrete category of the objects of \mathbf{C} , into $\bar{\mathbf{C}}$. The embedding $ob(\mathbf{C}) \rightarrow \bar{\mathbf{C}}$ forms a sesquistrict category and it is equivalent (as a rig category) to the original \mathbf{C} [11, Corollary 4.5]. Through the paper, when dealing with a rig category \mathbf{C} , we will often implicitly refer to the equivalent sesquistrict $ob(\mathbf{C}) \rightarrow \bar{\mathbf{C}}$.

Hereafter, we write A, B, \dots for the elements of a fixed set \mathcal{S} and U, V, \dots for the words in \mathcal{S}^* . Given two words $U, V \in \mathcal{S}^*$, we write $U \otimes V$, shortly UV , for their concatenation and 1 for the empty word. We use P, Q, \dots for words of words in $(\mathcal{S}^*)^*$ and we write $P \oplus Q$ for their concatenation and 0 for the empty word of words. Beyond \oplus , one can define \otimes on $(\mathcal{S}^*)^*$: for all $P = U_0 \oplus \dots \oplus U_n$ and $Q = V_0 \oplus \dots \oplus V_m$

$$P \otimes Q \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} U_0 V_0 \oplus \dots \oplus U_0 V_n \oplus \dots \oplus U_n V_0 \oplus \dots \oplus U_n V_m \tag{14}$$

For instance, $(A \oplus B) \otimes (C \oplus D)$ is $(A \otimes C) \oplus (A \otimes D) \oplus (B \otimes C) \oplus (B \otimes D)$. One can readily see that elements in $(\mathcal{S}^*)^*$ are in bijective correspondence with non-commutative *polynomials* with variables in \mathcal{S} . Consequently, we will call *monomials* the words in \mathcal{S}^* .

Given a set of sorts \mathcal{S} , a *monoidal signature* is a tuple $(\mathcal{S}, \Sigma, ar, coar)$ where ar and $coar$ assign to each symbol $s \in \Sigma$ an arity and a coarity in \mathcal{S}^* . A *rig signature* is the same but with arity and coarity in $(\mathcal{S}^*)^*$. An *interpretation* \mathcal{I} of a rig signature $(\mathcal{S}, \Sigma, ar, coar)$ in a sesquistrict rig category $H: \mathbf{M} \rightarrow \mathbf{D}$ is a pair of functions $(\alpha_{\mathcal{S}}: \mathcal{S} \rightarrow Ob(\mathbf{M}), \alpha_{\Sigma}: \Sigma \rightarrow Ar(\mathbf{D}))$ such that, for all $s \in \Sigma$, $\alpha_{\Sigma}(s)$ is an arrow having as domain and codomain $(\alpha_{\mathcal{S}}; H)^{\sharp}(ar(s))$ and $(\alpha_{\mathcal{S}}; H)^{\sharp}(coar(s))$. Here, $(\alpha_{\mathcal{S}}; H)^{\sharp}$ stands for inductive extension of $\alpha_{\mathcal{S}}; H: \mathcal{S} \rightarrow Ob(\mathbf{D})$ to $(\mathcal{S}^*)^*$.

Definition 5. Let $(\mathcal{S}, \Sigma, ar, coar)$ (simply Σ for short) be a rig signature. A sesquistrict rig category $H: \mathbf{M} \rightarrow \mathbf{D}$ is said to be *freely generated by Σ* if there is an interpretation $(\alpha_{\mathcal{S}}, \alpha_{\Sigma})$ of Σ in H such that for every sesquistrict rig category $H': \mathbf{M}' \rightarrow \mathbf{D}'$ and every interpretation $(\alpha'_{\mathcal{S}}: \mathcal{S} \rightarrow Ob(\mathbf{M}'), \alpha'_{\Sigma}: \Sigma \rightarrow Ar(\mathbf{D}'))$ there exists a unique sesquistrict rig functor $(\alpha: \mathbf{M} \rightarrow \mathbf{M}', \beta: \mathbf{D} \rightarrow \mathbf{D}')$ such that $\alpha_{\mathcal{S}}; \alpha = \alpha'_{\mathcal{S}}$ and $\alpha_{\Sigma}; \beta = \alpha'_{\Sigma}$.

6 Kleene-Cartesian Bicategories

We have seen that Cartesian bicategories provide enough structure for the allegorical fragment of CR, while Kleene bicategories for its Kleene fragment. For the whole CR, we make the Cartesian and Kleene bicategory structures interact as rig categories.

Definition 6. A Kleene-Cartesian rig category (shortly *kc rig*) is a poset enriched rig category \mathbf{C} such that

1. $(\mathbf{C}, \oplus, 0)$ is a Kleene bicategory;
2. $(\mathbf{C}, \otimes, 1)$ is a Cartesian bicategory;
3. the (co)monoids satisfy the following coherence conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleleft_{X \otimes Y} &= (\blacktriangleleft_X \oplus \blacktriangleleft_Y); (id_{XX} \oplus \mathring{\imath}_{XY} \oplus \mathring{\imath}_{YX} \oplus id_{YY}); (\delta_{X,X,Y}^{-l} \oplus \delta_{Y,X,Y}^{-l}) \quad !_{X \otimes Y} = (!_X \oplus !_Y); \triangleright_1 \\ \blacktriangleright_{X \otimes Y} &= (\blacktriangleright_X \oplus \blacktriangleright_Y); (id_{XX} \oplus \mathring{\imath}_{XY} \oplus \mathring{\imath}_{YX} \oplus id_{YY}); (\delta_{X,X,Y}^l \oplus \delta_{Y,X,Y}^l) \quad i_{X \otimes Y} = \triangleleft_1; (i_X \oplus i_Y) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

A morphism of kc rig-categories is a poset enriched rig functor that is a morphism of both Kleene and Cartesian bicategories.

The axioms in (15) rule the interaction of black and white (co)monoids. Recall that in Cartesian and Kleene bicategories, homsets carry respectively meet and join semilattices. In any kc rig category, they carry distributive lattices; also $(\cdot)^{\dagger}$ distributes over \oplus , while $(\cdot)^*$ only distributes laxly over \otimes . As expected $(\cdot^*)^{\dagger} = (\cdot^{\dagger})^*$.

Proposition 2. The laws in Table 3 hold in any kc rig category.

Corollary 2. Any kc rig category is a typed Kleene algebra with converse [17,8].

We have already seen that $(\mathbf{Rel}, \oplus, 0)$ is a Kleene bicategory and $(\mathbf{Rel}, \otimes, 1)$ is a Cartesian bicategory. To conclude that \mathbf{Rel} is a kc rig category, it is enough to check the coherence conditions of the two (co)monoids defined in (4).

$$\frac{f \sqcap (g \sqcup h) = (f \sqcap g) \sqcup (f \sqcap h) \quad f \sqcap \perp = \perp \quad f \sqcup (g \sqcap h) = (f \sqcup g) \sqcap (f \sqcup h) \quad f \sqcup \top = \top}{(f \otimes g)^* \leq f^* \otimes g^* \quad (f \oplus g)^\dagger = f^\dagger \oplus g^\dagger \quad (f \sqcap g)^* \leq f^* \sqcap g^* \quad (f \sqcup g)^\dagger = f^\dagger \sqcup g^\dagger \quad (f^\dagger)^* = (f^*)^\dagger}$$

Table 3: Derived laws in kc rig categories.

6.1 Kleene-Cartesian Tape Diagrams

We identify the kc rig category freely generated by a rig signature (\mathcal{S}, Σ) . This is described as *Kleene-Cartesian tape diagrams*, which provide a syntax for kc rig categories. These are strictly more expressive than the calculus of relations: thanks to the monoidal product \otimes , they can deal with n -ary function symbols, e.g. “add” in Equation (22), data flow and relational Hoare logic (Remark 3).

Thanks to Theorem 4.9 in [11], we can restrict, without loss of generality, to the simpler case where Σ is just a monoidal signature. Our work extends [11, Section 7] that identifies a freely generated *fb-cb rig category*, shortly a kc rig category without traces (\oplus is just a fb category with idempotent convolution).

As explained in Section 5, we can consider the sesquistrict rig categories having as sets of objects $(\mathcal{S}^*)^*$. For arrows, consider the following two-layer grammar

$$\begin{aligned} c &::= id_A \mid id_1 \mid s \mid \sigma_{A,B} \mid c; c \mid c \otimes c \mid !_A \mid \blacktriangleleft_A \mid i_A \mid \blacktriangleright_A \\ t &::= id_U \mid id_0 \mid \overline{c} \mid \sigma_{U,V}^\oplus \mid t; t \mid t \oplus t \mid \downarrow_U \mid \blacktriangleleft_U \mid \uparrow_U \mid \blacktriangleright_U \mid \text{tr}_U t \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $s \in \Sigma$, $A, B \in \mathcal{S}$ and $U, V \in \mathcal{S}^*$. The terms of the first row, called *circuits*, intuitively represent arrows of a Cartesian bicategory. The terms of the second row, called *tapes*, represent arrows of a Kleene bicategory. As expected, we only consider those terms to which is possible to associate source and target objects: the reader may check the simple type system in [9, Table 1]. Constants and operations in (16) can be extended to arbitrary polynomials in $(\mathcal{S}^*)^*$. For instance, $\text{tr}_P t$ is inductively defined as $\text{tr}_0(t) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} t$ and $\text{tr}_{U \oplus P}(t) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{tr}_P \text{tr}_U(t)$. For the other definitions see [11].

Particularly interesting is the fact that one can define \otimes on tapes: for $t_1: P \rightarrow Q$, $t_2: R \rightarrow S$, $t_1 \otimes t_2 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} L_P(t_2); R_S(t_1)$ where $L_P(\cdot)$, $R_S(\cdot)$ are the left and right whiskerings that can be defined by extending [11, Def 5.7] with an extra case for the trace: $L_U(\text{tr}_V t) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{tr}_{UV} L_U(t)$ and $R_U(\text{tr}_V t) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{tr}_{VU} R_U(t)$. Left distributors $\delta_{P,Q,R}^l: P \otimes (Q \oplus R) \rightarrow (P \otimes Q) \oplus (P \otimes R)$ and \otimes -symmetries $\sigma_{P,Q}^\otimes: P \otimes Q \rightarrow Q \otimes P$ are defined as in [11, Table 4]. The (co)monoids of \otimes as in [11, (20),(21)].

Next, we impose the laws of kc rig categories on tapes. However, this should be done carefully, in order to properly tackle the two uniformity laws (AU1) and (AU2) which are implications and not (in)equalities. Let \mathbb{I} be a set of pairs (t_1, t_2) of tapes with the same domain and codomain. We define $\leq_{\mathbb{I}}$ to be the set generated by the following

inference system (where $t \leq_I s$ is a shorthand for $(t, s) \in \leq_I$).

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \frac{t_1 \mathbb{I} t_2}{t_1 \leq_I t_2} \text{ (I)} \qquad \frac{-}{t \leq_I t} \text{ (r)} \qquad \frac{t_1 \leq_I t_2 \quad t_2 \leq_I t_3}{t_1 \leq_I t_3} \text{ (t)} \\
 \\
 \frac{t_1 \leq_I t_2 \quad s_1 \leq_I s_2}{t_1; s_1 \leq_I t_2; s_2} \text{ (;}) \qquad \frac{t_1 \leq_I t_2 \quad s_1 \leq_I s_2}{t_1 \oplus s_1 \leq_I t_2 \oplus s_2} \text{ (}\oplus\text{)} \qquad \frac{t_1 \leq_I t_2 \quad s_1 \leq_I s_2}{t_1 \otimes s_1 \leq_I t_2 \otimes s_2} \text{ (}\otimes\text{)} \qquad \text{(17)} \\
 \\
 \frac{s_2 \leq_I s_1 \quad t_1; (s_1 \oplus id) \leq_I (s_2 \oplus id); t_2}{\text{tr}_{s_1} t_1 \leq_I \text{tr}_{s_2} t_2} \text{ (u}_r\text{)} \qquad \frac{s_2 \leq_I s_1 \quad (s_1 \oplus id); t_1 \leq_I t_2; (s_2 \oplus id)}{\text{tr}_{s_1} t_1 \leq_I \text{tr}_{s_2} t_2} \text{ (u}_l\text{)}
 \end{array}$$

The first six laws ensure that \leq_I is a precongruence (w.r.t. $;$, \oplus and \otimes) containing \mathbb{I} . The last two rules force the uniformity laws: observe that, while in (AU1) and (AU2) the same arrow r occurs in both the left and the right-hand-side of the premises, here r is replaced by two different but related tapes s_1 and s_2 . This technicality is needed to guarantee uniformity in the category resulting from the following construction.

We take $\mathbb{K}\mathbb{C}$ to be the set of all pairs of tapes containing the axioms in Table 7⁵ and define $\leq_{\mathbb{K}\mathbb{C}}$ according to (17). We fix $\sim_{\mathbb{K}\mathbb{C}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \leq_{\mathbb{K}\mathbb{C}} \cap \geq_{\mathbb{K}\mathbb{C}}$. With these definitions we can construct the category of Kleene-Cartesian tapes \mathbf{KCT}_Σ : objects are polynomials in $(S^*)^*$ with \oplus and \otimes defined as in (14); arrows are $\sim_{\mathbb{K}\mathbb{C}}$ -equivalence classes of tapes; every homset $\mathbf{KCT}_\Sigma[P, Q]$ is ordered by $\leq_{\mathbb{K}\mathbb{C}}$. The construction of \mathbf{KCT}_Σ gives rise to a sesquistrict kc rig category. More importantly, \mathbf{KCT}_Σ is the freely generated one.

Theorem 2. \mathbf{KCT}_Σ is the free sesquistrict kc rig category generated by (S, Σ) .

In [11], it is shown that a key feature of tapes is that they can be drawn nicely in 2 dimensions despite representing arrows of rig categories. Indeed, both circuits and tapes can be drawn as string diagrams. Note however that *inside* tapes, there are string diagrams. Thus, the grammar in (16) can be graphically rendered as follows.

The identity id_0 is rendered as the empty tape \square , while id_1 is \blacksquare : a tape filled with the empty circuit. For a monomial $U = A_1 \dots A_n$, id_U is depicted as a tape containing n wires labelled by A_i . For instance, id_{AB} is rendered as \blacksquare_{AB} . When clear from the context, we will simply represent it as a single wire $u \blacksquare u$ with the appropriate label. Similarly, for a polynomial $P = \bigoplus_{i=1}^n U_i$, id_P is obtained as a vertical composition of tapes, as illustrated below on the left.

⁵ These rules are at the end of the paper, since we will soon draw them as diagrams.

The diagonal $\triangleleft_U : U \rightarrow U \oplus U$ is represented as a splitting of tapes, while the bang $\downarrow_U : U \rightarrow 0$ is a tape closed on its right boundary. Codiagonals and cobangs are represented in the same way but mirrored along the y-axis. Exploiting the usual coherence conditions e.g. in [55, Table 4.7], we can construct (co)diagonals and (co)bangs for arbitrary polynomials. For example, $\triangleright_{A \oplus B \oplus C}$ and $\uparrow_{A \oplus B \oplus C}$ are depicted as the second and third diagrams above.

The copier $\blacktriangleleft_A : A \rightarrow A \otimes A$ is represented as a splitting of wires, while the discharger $!_A : A \rightarrow 1$ is a wire closed on the right. From the coherence laws in (15), one can build (co)copiers and (co)dischargers for arbitrary polynomials. For instance, $\blacktriangleleft_{A \oplus B} : A \oplus B \rightarrow (A \oplus B) \otimes (A \oplus B) = AA \oplus AB \oplus BA \oplus BB$ and $!_{A \oplus B} : A \oplus B \rightarrow 1$ are drawn as the last two diagrams above.

For an arbitrary tape diagram $t : P \rightarrow Q$ we write $\begin{matrix} P & Q \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ t & \\ \vdots & \vdots \end{matrix}$.

The graphical representation embodies several axioms such as those of monoidal categories and several axioms for traces. Those axioms which are not implicit in the graphical representation are illustrated in Figures 2 and 3. Figure 4 illustrates the uniformity laws in the form of tape diagrams.

6.2 Kleene-Cartesian Theories and Functorial Semantics

A *Kleene-Cartesian theory*, shortly *kc theory*, is a pair (Σ, \mathbb{I}) where Σ is a monoidal signature and \mathbb{I} is a set of pairs (t_1, t_2) of tapes with same domain and codomain. Hereafter, we think of each pair (t_1, t_2) as an inequation $t_1 \leq t_2$, but the results that we develop in this section trivially hold also for equations: it is enough to add in \mathbb{I} a pair (t_2, t_1) for each $(t_1, t_2) \in \mathbb{I}$. Hereafter we always keep implicit $\mathbb{K}\mathbb{C}$ and we write $\leq_{\mathbb{I}}$ for $\leq_{\mathbb{K}\mathbb{C}\mathbb{I}}$ where the latter is defined as in (17). We fix $\sim_{\mathbb{I}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \leq_{\mathbb{I}} \cap \geq_{\mathbb{I}}$.

Recall that an interpretation $\mathcal{I} = (\alpha_S, \alpha_\Sigma)$ of a monoidal signature (S, Σ) in a sesquistrict rig category \mathbf{C} consists of $\alpha_S : S \rightarrow \text{Ob}(\mathbf{C})$ and $\alpha_\Sigma : \Sigma \rightarrow \text{Ar}(\mathbf{C})$. Whenever \mathbf{C} is a kc rig category, \mathcal{I} gives rises uniquely, by freeness of \mathbf{KCT}_Σ , to a morphism of kc rig categories $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} : \mathbf{KCT}_\Sigma \rightarrow \mathbf{C}$ defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket s \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= \alpha_\Sigma(s) & \llbracket id_A \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= id_{\alpha_S(A)} & \llbracket \blacktriangleleft_A \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= \blacktriangleleft_{\alpha_S(A)} & \llbracket !_A \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= !_{\alpha_S(A)} & \llbracket c; d \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= \llbracket c \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} ; \llbracket d \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} \\ \llbracket \sigma_{A,B}^\otimes \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= \sigma_{\alpha_S(A), \alpha_S(B)}^\otimes & \llbracket id_1 \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= id_1 & \llbracket \blacktriangleright_A \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= \blacktriangleright_{\alpha_S(A)} & \llbracket i_A \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= i_{\alpha_S(A)} & \llbracket c \otimes d \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= \llbracket c \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} \otimes \llbracket d \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} \\ \llbracket \bar{c} \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= \llbracket c \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} & \llbracket id_U \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= id_{\alpha_S^\#(U)} & \llbracket \triangleleft_U \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= \triangleleft_{\alpha_S^\#(U)} & \llbracket \downarrow_U \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= \downarrow_{\alpha_S^\#(U)} & \llbracket s; t \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= \llbracket s \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} ; \llbracket t \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} \\ \llbracket \sigma_{U,V}^\oplus \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= \sigma_{\alpha_S^\#(U), \alpha_S^\#(V)}^\oplus & \llbracket id_0 \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= id_0 & \llbracket \triangleright_U \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= \triangleright_{\alpha_S^\#(U)} & \llbracket \uparrow_U \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= \uparrow_{\alpha_S^\#(U)} & \llbracket s \oplus t \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= \llbracket s \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} \oplus \llbracket t \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} \\ & & & & \llbracket tr_U t \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} &= tr_{\alpha_S^\#(U)} \llbracket t \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} \end{aligned}$$

We say that an interpretation \mathcal{I} of Σ is a *model of the theory* (Σ, \mathbb{I}) whenever $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}}$ preserves $\leq_{\mathbb{I}}$: if $t_1 \leq_{\mathbb{I}} t_2$, then $\llbracket t_1 \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}}$ is below $\llbracket t_2 \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}}$ in \mathbf{C} . Models enjoy a beautiful characterisation provided by Proposition 3 below. Let $\mathbf{KCT}_{\Sigma, \mathbb{I}}$ be the category having the same objects as \mathbf{KCT}_Σ and arrows $\sim_{\mathbb{I}}$ -equivalence classes of arrows of \mathbf{KCT}_Σ ordered by $\leq_{\mathbb{I}}$. Since \mathbf{KCT}_Σ is a kc rig category, then also $\mathbf{KCT}_{\Sigma, \mathbb{I}}$ is so.

Fig. 2: Tape axioms for Kleene bicategory

Proposition 3. *Let (Σ, \mathbb{I}) be a kc tape theory and \mathbf{C} a sesquistrict kc rig category. Models of (Σ, \mathbb{I}) are in bijective correspondence with morphisms of sesquistrict kc rig categories from $\mathbf{KCT}_{\Sigma, \mathbb{I}}$ to \mathbf{C} .*

Example 1 (Functions). Let \mathcal{S} be a set of sorts and $\Sigma \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{f: U \rightarrow A\}$ for some $A \in \mathcal{S}$ and $U \in \mathcal{S}^*$. Let \mathbb{I} be the set of the two equalities in (18). An interpretation \mathcal{I} of (Σ, Σ) in \mathbf{Rel} , consists of a set $\alpha_{\mathcal{S}}(A_i)$ for each $A_i \in \mathcal{S}$ and a relation $\alpha_{\Sigma}(f) \subseteq \alpha_{\mathcal{S}}^{\sharp}(U) \times \alpha_{\mathcal{S}}(A)$. \mathcal{I} is a model of (Σ, \mathbb{I}) iff $\alpha_{\Sigma}(f)$ is single valued (**SV**) and total (**TOT**), i.e., a function.

$$\begin{array}{c} U \\ \bullet \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} \downarrow f \\ \uparrow f \end{array} \right] \\ \bullet \\ A \end{array} \leq \begin{array}{c} U \\ \bullet \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} \leftarrow f \\ \rightarrow f \end{array} \right] \\ \bullet \\ A \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} U \\ \bullet \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} \leftarrow f \\ \rightarrow f \end{array} \right] \\ \bullet \\ A \end{array} \leq \begin{array}{c} U \\ \bullet \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} \leftarrow f \\ \rightarrow f \end{array} \right] \\ \bullet \\ A \end{array} \quad (18)$$

Fig. 3: Axioms of Cartesian bicategories

Fig. 4: Posetal uniformity axioms in tape diagrams.

Example 2 (KAT). Let \mathcal{P} be a set of predicate symbols $R: U \rightarrow 1$ for $U \in \mathcal{S}^*$. Take $\bar{\mathcal{P}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{\bar{R}: U \rightarrow 1 \mid R \in \mathcal{P}\}$ and $\Sigma \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathcal{P} \cup \bar{\mathcal{P}}$. Let \mathbb{I} be the set of equalities below.

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{Diagram with } R \text{ and } \bar{R} \text{ boxes} \\
 \text{Diagram with } R \text{ box} \\
 \text{Diagram with } \bar{R} \text{ box}
 \end{array}
 =
 \begin{array}{c}
 \text{Diagram with } R \text{ box} \\
 \text{Diagram with } \bar{R} \text{ box}
 \end{array}
 \quad (19)$$

An interpretation \mathcal{I} of (\mathcal{S}, Σ) in \mathbf{Rel} is a set $\alpha_{\mathcal{S}}(A_i)$ for each $A_i \in \mathcal{S}$ together with predicates $R \subseteq X \times 1$ and $\bar{R} \subseteq X \times 1$ for $X \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \alpha_{\mathcal{S}}^{\#}(U)$. \mathcal{I} is a model iff, for all R, \bar{R} is its set-theoretic complement: by (13) and (5), the equalities above asserts that $R \cup \bar{R} = X$ and $R \cap \bar{R} = \{\}$. By Proposition 2, $\mathbf{KCT}_{\Sigma, \mathbb{I}}[U, 1]$ carries a distributive lattice and even a Boolean algebra when defining $\neg P$, for all $P: U \rightarrow 1$ as follows.

$$\neg R \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \bar{R} \quad \neg \top \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \perp \quad \neg(P \sqcup Q) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \neg P \sqcap \neg Q \quad \neg \bar{R} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} R \quad \neg \perp \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \top \quad \neg(P \sqcap Q) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \neg P \sqcup \neg Q \quad (20)$$

Consider the set C that contains, for each $P: U \rightarrow 1$, the associated coreflexive:

$$c(P) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} u \text{ [Diagram with } P \text{ box]} u \quad (\text{drawn as } u \text{ [Diagram with } P \text{ box]} u) \quad (21)$$

Again coreflexives form a Boolean algebra $(C, \sqcup, \sqcap, \neg, \perp, id)$ where composition $;$ acts as \sqcap : see Lemma 2.3. Moreover, by Corollary 1, $\mathbf{KCT}_{\Sigma, \mathbb{I}}[U, U]$ is a Kleene algebra. Thus $(\mathbf{KCT}_{\Sigma, \mathbb{I}}[U, U], C, \sqcup, \sqcap, \neg, \perp, id, \neg)$ is a Kleene algebra with tests [42].

Fig. 5: The Kleene-Cartesian theory of Peano.

Remark 2. Recall CR from Section 2. The set Σ of generating symbols corresponds to a monoidal signature where $\mathcal{S} = \{A\}$ and each symbol has both arity and coarity A . A relational interpretation of CR is exactly an interpretation \mathcal{I} of the monoidal signature (\mathcal{S}, Σ) into **Rel**. One can define an inductive encoding $\mathcal{E}(\cdot)$ from CR to \mathbf{KCT}_{Σ} by using (5) and (13). A simple inductive argument confirms that, for all interpretations \mathcal{I} and expressions $E \in \text{CR}$, $\langle E \rangle_{\mathcal{I}} = \llbracket \mathcal{E}(E) \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}}$. Thus, if $\mathcal{E}(E_1) \leq_{\mathbf{KCT}} \mathcal{E}(E_2)$, then $E_1 \leq_{\text{CR}} E_2$.

7 The Kleene-Cartesian Theory of Peano

In this section we illustrate a further example of kc theory: Peano’s axiomatisation of natural numbers. Recall that such axiomatisation is not a first order theory [32].

We commence by fixing the signature: $\mathcal{S} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{A\}$ and $\Sigma \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{ \boxed{0} \dashv A, A \dashv \boxed{s} \dashv A \}$. An interpretation of Σ in **Rel** consists of a set X (i.e., $\alpha_{\Sigma}(A)$), a relation $0 \subseteq 1 \times X$ (i.e., $\alpha_{\Sigma}(\boxed{0} \dashv A)$) and a relation $s \subseteq X \times X$ (i.e., $\alpha_{\Sigma}(A \dashv \boxed{s} \dashv A)$). The set of axioms \mathbb{P} consists of those in Figure 5.

From a universal-algebraic perspective, natural numbers are the smallest set X such that X is isomorphic to $X \oplus 1$. The two leftmost axioms in Figure 5 force $[s, 0] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (s \oplus 0); \triangleright_X$ to be an isomorphism of type $X \oplus 1 \rightarrow X$: (iso-1) states that $[s, 0]^{\dagger}; [s, 0] = id_X$; (iso-2) that $[s, 0]; [s, 0]^{\dagger} = id_{X \oplus 1}$; the rightmost the fact that it is the smallest: i.e. $X \subseteq 0$; $s^* : 1 \rightarrow X$. One can similarly obtain any algebraic data type.

We illustrate that (Σ, \mathbb{P}) is equivalent to Peano’s axiomatisation of natural numbers. Possibly, the most interesting axiom is the principle of induction: (ind-princ) in Figure 6. This follows easily from posetal uniformity and (ind).

Theorem 3 (Principle of Induction). *Let (Π, \mathbb{Q}) be a kc theory, such that $\Sigma \subseteq \Pi$ and $\mathbb{P} \subseteq \mathbb{Q}$. For all $P : 1 \rightarrow A$ in $\mathbf{KCT}_{\Pi, \mathbb{Q}}$, (ind-princ) in Figure 6 holds*

Proof. Observe that the following holds:

Thus, by (AU2) the inclusion below holds and the derivation concludes the proof.

The other Peano’s axioms state that 0 is a natural number, s is an injective function and that 0 is *not* the successor of any natural number. These are illustrated by means of

Fig. 6: Peano’s theory of the natural numbers.

tapes in Figure 6, where we use the characterisation of total, single valued and injective relations provided by Lemma 1. Observe that (\perp) states that $\{x \in X \mid (x, 0) \in s\} \subseteq \emptyset$.

Lemma 3. *The laws in Figures 5 and 6 are equivalent.*

In [25], Dedekind showed that any two models of Peano’s axioms are isomorphic, and thus any model of (Σ, \mathbb{P}) is isomorphic to the one on natural numbers. To give to the reader a taste of how one can program with tapes, we now illustrate how to start to encode arithmetic within (Σ, \mathbb{P}) . The tape for addition is illustrated on the right. Such tape can be thought as a simple imperative program:


```
add(x,y) = while (x>0) { x:=x-1; y:=y+1 }; return y
```

The variable x corresponds to the top wire in (22), while y to the bottom one. At any iteration, the program checks whether x is 0, in which case it returns y , or the successor of some number, in which case x takes such number, while y takes its own successor.

In [9, Lemma 10.3] we show that (22) satisfies the usual inductive definition of addition, namely:

$$A \begin{array}{c} \boxed{0} \\ \boxed{+} \end{array} A \leq_{\mathbb{P}} A \text{---} A \quad A \begin{array}{c} \boxed{s} \\ \boxed{+} \end{array} A \leq_{\mathbb{P}} A \begin{array}{c} \boxed{+} \\ \boxed{s} \end{array} A .$$

While, it is straightforward that $A \begin{array}{c} \boxed{+} \\ \boxed{+} \end{array} A$ terminates on all possible inputs, it is interesting to see how this can be proved within the kc theory (Σ, \mathbb{P}) .

Lemma 4. *The tape $A \begin{array}{c} \boxed{+} \\ \boxed{+} \end{array} A$ is total, i.e. $A \begin{array}{c} \bullet \\ \bullet \end{array} A \leq_{\mathbb{P}} A \begin{array}{c} \boxed{+} \\ \boxed{+} \end{array} A$.*

Proof. First observe that the following holds:

Then, by (AUI), the inequality below holds and the derivation concludes the proof.

$\frac{}{\Gamma, x: A, \Delta \vdash x: A}$ (VAR)	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash e_i: A_i \quad f: A_1 \otimes \dots \otimes A_n \rightarrow A}{\Gamma \vdash f(e_1, \dots, e_n): A}$ (OP)	
$\frac{}{\Gamma \vdash \top: 1}$ (TOP)	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash P: 1 \quad \Gamma \vdash Q: 1}{\Gamma \vdash (P \wedge Q): 1}$ (AND)	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash e_i: A_i \quad R: A_1 \otimes \dots \otimes A_n \rightarrow 1}{\Gamma \vdash \bar{R}(e_1, \dots, e_n): 1}$ (\bar{R})
$\frac{}{\Gamma \vdash \perp: 1}$ (BOT)	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash P: 1 \quad \Gamma \vdash Q: 1}{\Gamma \vdash (P \vee Q): 1}$ (OR)	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash e_i: A_i \quad R: A_1 \otimes \dots \otimes A_n \rightarrow 1}{\Gamma \vdash R(e_1, \dots, e_n): 1}$ (R)
$\frac{}{\Gamma \vdash \text{abort}}$ (ABORT)	$\frac{}{\Gamma \vdash \text{skip}}$ (SKIP)	$\frac{\Gamma = \Gamma', x: A, \Delta' \quad \Gamma \vdash e: A}{\Gamma \vdash x := e}$ (ASSN)
$\frac{\Gamma \vdash C \quad \Gamma \vdash D}{\Gamma \vdash C; D}$ (;)	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash P: 1 \quad \Gamma \vdash C}{\Gamma \vdash \text{while } P \text{ do } C}$ (WHILE)	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash P: 1 \quad \Gamma \vdash C \quad \Gamma \vdash D}{\Gamma \vdash \text{if } P \text{ then } C \text{ else } D}$ (IF)

Table 4: Type system for expressions, predicates and commands.

8 Diagrammatic Hoare Logic

We now illustrate how tape diagrams can provide a comfortable setting to reason about imperative programs. For the sake of generality, we avoid to fix basic types and operations and, rather, we work parametrically with respect to a triple $(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{P})$: \mathcal{S} is a set of sorts, representing basic types; \mathcal{F} is a set of function symbols, equipped with an arity in \mathcal{S}^* and a coarity in \mathcal{S} ; \mathcal{P} is a set of predicate symbols equipped just with an arity in \mathcal{S}^* . The coarity of predicates is fixed to be 1.

We take the signature $\Sigma \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{P} \cup \bar{\mathcal{P}}$ where $\bar{\mathcal{P}}$ is as in Example 2. The set \mathbb{I} contains, for all $f: U \rightarrow A$ in \mathcal{F} , the axioms in (18) and, for each $R: U \rightarrow 1$ in \mathcal{P} , those in (19). One may add to \mathbb{I} other axioms, e.g., those of \mathbb{P} in Section 7.

We consider terms generated by the following grammar

$$\begin{aligned}
e &::= x \mid f(e_1, \dots, e_n) \\
P &::= R(e_1, \dots, e_n) \mid \bar{R}(e_1, \dots, e_n) \mid \top \mid \perp \mid P \vee P \mid P \wedge P \\
C &::= \text{abort} \mid \text{skip} \mid \text{if } P \text{ then } C \text{ else } D \mid \text{while } P \text{ do } C \mid C; D \mid x := e
\end{aligned}$$

where $f \in \mathcal{F}$, $R \in \mathcal{P}$ and x is taken from a fixed set of variables. As usual, e are expressions, P predicates and C commands. Negation of predicates can be expressed as in (20). In order to encode terms into diagrams, we need to make copying and discarding of variables explicit; we thus define a simple type systems with judgement of the form

$$\Gamma \vdash e: A \quad \Gamma \vdash P: 1 \quad \Gamma \vdash C$$

where A is a sort in \mathcal{S} and Γ is a *typing context*, i.e., an ordered sequence $x_1: A_1, \dots, x_n: A_n$, where all the x_i are distinct variables and $A_i \in \mathcal{S}$. The type system is in Table 4.

The encoding of terms into diagrams, presented in Table 5, is defined inductively on the typing rules. For instance, in the encoding of the assignment $\Gamma \vdash x := e$, the context is $\Gamma = \Gamma', x: A, \Delta'$, according to the typing rule (ASSN).

The encoding $\mathcal{E}(\cdot)$ maps well typed expressions $\Gamma \vdash e: A$, predicates $\Gamma \vdash P: 1$ and commands $\Gamma \vdash C$ into, respectively, diagrams of the following types

$$\mathcal{E}(\Gamma) \rightarrow A \quad \mathcal{E}(\Gamma) \rightarrow 1 \quad \mathcal{E}(\Gamma) \rightarrow \mathcal{E}(\Gamma)$$

where for $\Gamma = x_1: A_1, \dots, x_n: A_n$, we fix $\mathcal{E}(\Gamma) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} A_1 \otimes \dots \otimes A_n$. In the encoding of expressions and predicates, we use $\blacktriangleleft_{\mathcal{E}(\Gamma)}^n$ to copy n times the content of variables in

Proof. By induction on the rules in Table 6. We illustrate only two cases: the others can be found in the proof of [9, Proposition 11.5]. For (assn), observe that by Lemma 5, $\mathcal{E}(P[e/x])^\dagger ; \mathcal{E}(x := e)$ is the leftmost diagram below. Thus:

$$\begin{array}{c} \boxed{\mathcal{E}(P)} \quad \boxed{\mathcal{E}(e)} \quad \boxed{\mathcal{E}(e)} \quad \begin{array}{l} \Gamma \\ A \\ A \end{array} \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \end{array} \stackrel{(\text{nat})}{\leq_{\mathbb{I}}} \begin{array}{c} \boxed{\mathcal{E}(P)} \quad \boxed{\mathcal{E}(e)} \quad \boxed{\mathcal{E}(e)} \quad \begin{array}{l} \Gamma \\ A \\ A \end{array} \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \end{array} \stackrel{(6)}{\leq_{\mathbb{I}}} \begin{array}{c} \boxed{\mathcal{E}(P)} \quad \begin{array}{l} \Gamma \\ A \\ A \end{array} \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \end{array} .$$

For (while), observe that the following holds:

$$\begin{array}{c} \boxed{\mathcal{E}(P)} \quad \boxed{\mathcal{E}(B)} \quad \boxed{\mathcal{E}(C)} \quad \begin{array}{l} \Gamma \\ \Gamma \end{array} \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \end{array} \stackrel{(\triangleright\text{-nat})}{\stackrel{(\triangleleft\text{-nat})}{=_{\mathbb{I}}}} \begin{array}{c} \boxed{\mathcal{E}(P)} \quad \boxed{\mathcal{E}(B)} \quad \boxed{\mathcal{E}(C)} \quad \begin{array}{l} \Gamma \\ \Gamma \end{array} \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \end{array} \stackrel{(\text{Ind. hyp.})}{\leq_{\mathbb{I}}} \begin{array}{c} \boxed{\mathcal{E}(P)} \quad \boxed{\mathcal{E}(B)} \quad \boxed{\mathcal{E}(C)} \quad \begin{array}{l} \Gamma \\ \Gamma \end{array} \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \end{array} .$$

Then, by (AU2), the inequality below holds and the derivation concludes the proof.

$$\begin{array}{c} \boxed{\mathcal{E}(P)} \quad \boxed{\mathcal{E}(B)} \quad \boxed{\mathcal{E}(C)} \quad \begin{array}{l} \Gamma \\ \Gamma \end{array} \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \end{array} \stackrel{(\text{AU2})}{\leq_{\mathbb{I}}} \begin{array}{c} \boxed{\mathcal{E}(P)} \quad \boxed{\mathcal{E}(B)} \quad \boxed{\mathcal{E}(C)} \quad \begin{array}{l} \Gamma \\ \Gamma \end{array} \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \end{array} \stackrel{(\text{AT1})}{=_{\mathbb{I}}} \begin{array}{c} \boxed{\mathcal{E}(P)} \quad \boxed{\mathcal{E}(B)} \quad \begin{array}{l} \Gamma \\ \Gamma \end{array} \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \end{array} .$$

Remark 3 (Other Program Logics). The above result proves a syntactic correspondence amongst the deduction systems in Table 6 and $\leq_{\mathbb{I}}$. To prove such result we did not need to explicitly give the semantics of command or prove that our encoding preserves the semantics. However, assuming that, for a fixed interpretation \mathcal{I} , $\llbracket \mathcal{E}(\Gamma \vdash C) \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}}$ is the intended relational semantics of a command C , one can immediately see that the correspondence at the semantic level –illustrated below on the top-left corner– holds.

$$\begin{array}{l} \{P\}C\{Q\} \text{ iff } \llbracket \mathcal{E}(P)^\dagger ; \mathcal{E}(C) \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} \subseteq \llbracket \mathcal{E}(Q)^\dagger \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} \quad \langle\langle P \rangle\rangle C \langle\langle Q \rangle\rangle \text{ iff } \llbracket \mathcal{E}(P) \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} \subseteq \llbracket \mathcal{E}(C) ; \mathcal{E}(Q) \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} \\ [P]C[Q] \text{ iff } \llbracket \mathcal{E}(P)^\dagger ; \mathcal{E}(C) \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} \supseteq \llbracket \mathcal{E}(Q)^\dagger \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} \quad (P)C(Q) \text{ iff } \llbracket \mathcal{E}(P) \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} \supseteq \llbracket \mathcal{E}(C) ; \mathcal{E}(Q) \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} \end{array}$$

The other correspondences concern other logics: $[P]C[Q]$ are triples of incorrectness logic [50], $\langle\langle P \rangle\rangle C \langle\langle Q \rangle\rangle$ of sufficient incorrectness [2] and $(P)C(Q)$ of necessary [24]. Interestingly, quadruples of *relational Hoare logics* [7] can be characterised as

$$\llbracket \mathcal{E}(\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \vdash P : 1)^\dagger ; \mathcal{E}(\Gamma_1 \vdash C_1) \otimes \mathcal{E}(\Gamma_2 \vdash C_2) \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} \subseteq \llbracket \mathcal{E}(\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2 \vdash Q : 1)^\dagger \rrbracket_{\mathcal{I}} \quad (23)$$

9 Concluding remarks

We introduced Kleene bicategories and proved that they form Kleene algebras in Kozen’s sense (Corollary 1). By examining their interaction with Cartesian bicategories, we developed Kleene-Cartesian rig categories and characterised the free one as tape diagrams (Theorem 2). Furthermore, we showed that tape diagrams can express Kleene algebra with tests [42], Peano’s natural numbers, and various program logics. We proved that the rules of Hoare logic follow from the structure of kc rig categories (Proposition 4).

Regarding Kleene bicategories, while we are not the first to explore uniform traces over biproduct categories (see, e.g., [20]), the use of *posetal* uniformity and the correspondence with Kozen’s axioms are, to the best of our knowledge, novel contributions.

Computer scientists usually find control flow and data flow graphs intuitive. Tapes diagram combine the two in a single diagrammatic representation equipped with compositional semantics. Another key distinction of tape diagrams, compared to other relational or categorical approaches to program logics (e.g., [44,1,31,49,34,5]), lies in the \otimes monoidal and rig structures, which enable direct representation of *product programs* [6]. Through tape (in)equalities and \otimes , it becomes easy to express complex properties like *non-interference* [30]. Exploring how such properties can be proved by the laws of kc rig categories remains a promising direction for future research.

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$(f; g); h = f; (g; h) \quad id_X; f = f = f; id_Y$ $(f_1 \circ f_2); (g_1 \circ g_2) = (f_1; g_1) \circ (f_2; g_2)$ $id_I \circ f = f = f \circ id_I \quad (f \circ g) \circ h = f \circ (g \circ h)$ $\sigma_{A,B}^{\circ}; \sigma_{B,A}^{\circ} = id_{A \circ B} \quad (s \circ id_Z); \sigma_{Y,Z}^{\circ} = \sigma_{X,Z}^{\circ}; (id_Z \circ s)$	$tr_U((id \oplus u); t; (id \oplus v)) = u; tr_U t; v$ $tr_U(t \oplus s) = tr_U t \oplus s$ $tr_V tr_U t = tr_{U \otimes V} t \quad tr_0 t = t$ $tr_V(t; (u \oplus id)) = tr_U((u \oplus id); t) \quad tr_U \sigma_{U,U}^{\oplus} = id_U$
$\overline{\left\langle \! \! \left\langle A; (id_A \otimes \! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle \right\rangle \right\rangle} = \overline{\left\langle \! \! \left\langle A; (\! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle id_A) \right\rangle \right\rangle}$ $\overline{(id_A \otimes \! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle); \! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle} = \overline{(\! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle id_A); \! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle}$ $\overline{(id_A \otimes \! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle); (\! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle id_A)} = \overline{\! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle; \! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle} \quad \overline{id_A} = \overline{\! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle; \! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle}$ $\overline{id_A} \leq \overline{\! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle; \! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle} \quad \overline{\! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle; \! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle} \leq \overline{id_{A \otimes A}}$	$\overline{\! \! \left\langle A; (\! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle id_A)} = \overline{id_A} \quad \overline{\! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle; \sigma_{A,A}^{\otimes}} = \overline{\! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle}$ $\overline{(\! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle id_A); \! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle} = \overline{id_A} \quad \overline{\sigma_{A,A}^{\otimes}; \! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle} = \overline{\! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle}$ $\overline{s; \! \! \left\langle V \right\rangle} \leq \overline{\! \! \left\langle V \right\rangle; (s \otimes s)} \quad \overline{s; \! \! \left\langle V \right\rangle} \leq \overline{\! \! \left\langle V \right\rangle}$ $\overline{id_A} \leq \overline{\! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle; \! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle} \quad \overline{\! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle; \! \! \left\langle A \right\rangle} \leq \overline{id_{A \otimes A}}$
$\! \! \left\langle U; (id_U \oplus \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle) = \! \! \left\langle U; (\! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle id_U)$ $(id_U \oplus \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle); \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle = (\! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle id_U); \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle$ $\! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle = \! \! \left\langle U \oplus U; (\! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle) \quad \! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle = id_U$ $\overline{\! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle} = \! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle \quad \overline{\! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle} = \! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle$ $id_U \geq \! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle \quad \! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle \geq id_{U \oplus U}$	$\! \! \left\langle U; (\! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle id_U) = id_U \quad \! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle = \! \! \left\langle U \oplus U$ $(\! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle id_U); \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle = id_U \quad \! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle = \! \! \left\langle U \oplus U$ $\! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle = \! \! \left\langle U \oplus U \quad \! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle = \! \! \left\langle U \oplus U$ $\! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle = \! \! \left\langle U \oplus U \quad \! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle = \! \! \left\langle U \oplus U$ $id_U \geq \! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle \quad \! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle \geq id_U$
$tr_U(\! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle) = id_U \quad \overline{id_U} = id_U \quad \overline{\! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle} = \overline{\! \! \left\langle U; \! \! \left\langle U \right\rangle}$	

Table 7: Axioms for Kleene-Cartesian Tapes. For each axiom $l = r$ in top-left corner, the set $\mathbb{K}\mathbb{C}$ contains the pairs (l, r) and (r, l) where \circ and I are replaced by \oplus and 0 and the pairs $(\overline{l}, \overline{r})$ and $(\overline{r}, \overline{l})$ where \circ and I are replaced by \otimes and 1 . In the rest, for each $l \leq r$ $\mathbb{K}\mathbb{C}$ contains a pair (l, r) and, additionally, the pair (r, l) in case of an axiom $l = r$.

References

1. Aguirre, A., Katsumata, S.y.: Weakest preconditions in fibrations. *Electronic Notes in Theoretical Computer Science* **352**, 5–27 (2020)
2. Ascari, F., Bruni, R., Gori, R., Logozzo, F.: Sufficient incorrectness logic: SIL and separation SIL (2023)
3. Backens, M.: The zx-calculus is complete for stabilizer quantum mechanics. *New Journal of Physics* **16**(9), 093021 (2014)
4. Bainbridge, E.S.: Feedback and generalized logic. *Information and Control* **31**(1), 75–96 (1976)
5. Barrett, C., Castle, D., Heijltjes, W.: The relational machine calculus. In: Sobocinski, P., Lago, U.D., Esparza, J. (eds.) *Proceedings of the 39th Annual ACM/IEEE Symposium on Logic in Computer Science, LICS 2024, Tallinn, Estonia, July 8-11, 2024*. pp. 9:1–9:15. ACM (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3661814.3662091>
6. Barthe, G., Crespo, J.M., Kunz, C.: Relational verification using product programs. In: *International Symposium on Formal Methods*. pp. 200–214. Springer (2011)
7. Benton, N.: Simple relational correctness proofs for static analyses and program transformations. *ACM SIGPLAN Notices* **39**(1), 14–25 (2004)
8. Bloom, S.L., Ésik, Z., Stefanescu, G.: Notes on equational theories of relations. *Algebra Universalis* **33**(1), 98–126 (1995)
9. Bonchi, F., Di Giorgio, A., Di Lavore, E.: A diagrammatic algebra for program logics (2024), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2410.03561>
10. Bonchi, F., Di Giorgio, A., Haydon, N., Sobocinski, P.: Diagrammatic algebra of first order logic. In: Sobocinski, P., Lago, U.D., Esparza, J. (eds.) *Proceedings of the 39th Annual ACM/IEEE Symposium on Logic in Computer Science, LICS 2024, Tallinn, Estonia, July 8-11, 2024*. pp. 16:1–16:15. ACM (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3661814.3662078>
11. Bonchi, F., Di Giorgio, A., Santamaria, A.: Deconstructing the calculus of relations with tape diagrams. *Proceedings of the ACM on Programming Languages* **7**(POPL), 1864–1894 (2023)
12. Bonchi, F., Holland, J., Piedeleu, R., Sobociński, P., Zanasi, F.: Diagrammatic algebra: From linear to concurrent systems. *Proceedings of the ACM on Programming Languages* **3**(POPL), 25:1–25:28 (Jan 2019). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3290338>
13. Bonchi, F., Pavlovic, D., Sobocinski, P.: Functorial semantics for relational theories. arXiv preprint arXiv:1711.08699 (2017)
14. Bonchi, F., Piedeleu, R., Sobociński, P., Zanasi, F.: Graphical affine algebra. In: *Proceedings of the 34th Annual ACM/IEEE Symposium on Logic in Computer Science (LICS)*. pp. 1–12 (2019)
15. Bonchi, F., Seeber, J., Sobocinski, P.: Graphical Conjunctive Queries. In: Ghica, D., Jung, A. (eds.) *27th EACSL Annual Conference on Computer Science Logic (CSL 2018)*. Leibniz International Proceedings in Informatics (LIPIcs), vol. 119, pp. 13:1–13:23. Schloss Dagstuhl–Leibniz-Zentrum fuer Informatik, Dagstuhl, Germany (2018). <https://doi.org/10.4230/LIPIcs.CSL.2018.13>
16. Bonchi, F., Sobocinski, P., Zanasi, F.: Full abstraction for signal flow graphs. *ACM SIGPLAN Notices* **50**(1), 515–526 (2015)
17. Brunet, P., Pous, D.: Kleene algebra with converse. In: *Relational and Algebraic Methods in Computer Science: 14th International Conference, RAMiCS 2014, Marienstatt, Germany, April 28–May 1, 2014*. *Proceedings 14*. pp. 101–118. Springer (2014)
18. Bruni, R., Melgratti, H., Montanari, U.: Connector algebras, Petri nets, and BIP. In: *International Andrei Ershov Memorial Conference on Perspectives of System Informatics*. pp. 19–38. Springer (2011)

19. Carboni, A., Walters, R.F.C.: Cartesian bicategories I. *Journal of Pure and Applied Algebra* **49**, 11–32 (1987)
20. Căzănescu, V.E., Ştefănescu, G.: Feedback, iteration, and repetition. In: *Mathematical aspects of natural and formal languages*, pp. 43–61. World Scientific (1994)
21. Cockett, J.R.B., Koslowski, J., Seely, R.A.: Introduction to linear bicategories. *Mathematical Structures in Computer Science* **10**(2), 165–203 (2000)
22. Coecke, B., Duncan, R.: Interacting quantum observables: categorical algebra and diagrammatics. *New Journal of Physics* **13**(4), 043016 (2011)
23. Coecke, B., Selby, J., Tull, S.: Two Roads to Classicality **266**, 104–118 (Feb 2018). <https://doi.org/10.4204/EPTCS.266.7>
24. Cousot, P., Cousot, R., Fähndrich, M., Logozzo, F.: Automatic inference of necessary preconditions. In: Giacobazzi, R., Berdine, J., Mastroeni, I. (eds.) *Verification, Model Checking, and Abstract Interpretation, 14th International Conference, VMCAI 2013, Rome, Italy, January 20–22, 2013. Proceedings. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 7737, pp. 128–148. Springer (2013). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-35873-9_10
25. Dedekind, R.: The nature and meaning of numbers (1888)
26. Fong, B., Spivak, D.: String diagrams for regular logic (extended abstract). In: Baez, J., Coecke, B. (eds.) *Applied Category Theory 2019. Electronic Proceedings in Theoretical Computer Science*, vol. 323, p. 196–229. Open Publishing Association (Sep 2020). <https://doi.org/10.4204/eptcs.323.14>
27. Fox, T.: Coalgebras and cartesian categories. *Communications in Algebra* **4**(7), 665–667 (1976). <https://doi.org/10.1080/00927877608822127>
28. Fritz, T.: A presentation of the category of stochastic matrices. *CoRR* **abs/0902.2554** (2009)
29. Ghica, D.R., Jung, A.: Categorical semantics of digital circuits. In: *2016 Formal Methods in Computer-Aided Design (FMCAD)*. pp. 41–48 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1109/FMCAD.2016.7886659>
30. Goguen, J.A., Meseguer, J.: Unwinding and inference control. In: *1984 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy*. pp. 75–75. IEEE (1984)
31. Goncharov, S., Schröder, L.: A relatively complete generic hoare logic for order-enriched effects. In: *2013 28th Annual ACM/IEEE Symposium on Logic in Computer Science*. pp. 273–282. IEEE (2013)
32. Harsanyi, J.C.: Mathematics, the empirical facts, and logical necessity. *Erkenntnis* **19**(1), 167–192 (1983)
33. Hasegawa, M.: The uniformity principle on traced monoidal categories. *Electronic Notes in Theoretical Computer Science* **69**, 137–155 (2003)
34. Hasuo, I.: Generic weakest precondition semantics from monads enriched with order. *Theoretical Computer Science* **604**, 2–29 (2015)
35. Hoare, C.A.R.: An axiomatic basis for computer programming. *Communications of the ACM* **12**(10), 576–580 (1969)
36. John C. Baez, Brandon Coya, F.R.: Props in network theory. *CoRR* **abs/1707.08321** (2017), <http://arxiv.org/abs/1707.08321>
37. Johnson, N., Yau, D.: Bimonoidal categories, e_n -monoidal categories, and algebraic k -theory (2022), <https://nilesjohnson.net/En-monoidal.html>
38. Joyal, A., Street, R.: The geometry of tensor calculus, I. *Advances in Mathematics* **88**(1), 55–112 (Jul 1991). [https://doi.org/10.1016/0001-8708\(91\)90003-P](https://doi.org/10.1016/0001-8708(91)90003-P)
39. Joyal, A., Street, R., Verity, D.: Traced monoidal categories. *Math Procs Cambridge Philosophical Society* **119**(3), 447–468 (4 1996)
40. Katis, P., Sabadini, N., Walters, R.F.: Bicategories of processes. *Journal of Pure and Applied Algebra* **115**(2), 141–178 (1997)
41. Kozen, D.: A completeness theorem for kleene algebras and the algebra of regular events. *Information and Computation* **110**, 366–390 (1994)

42. Kozen, D.: Kleene algebra with tests. *ACM Transactions on Programming Languages and Systems (TOPLAS)* **19**(3), 427–443 (1997)
43. Kozen, D.: Typed Kleene algebra. Tech. Rep. TR98-1669, Computer Science Department, Cornell University (March 1998)
44. Kozen, D.: On Hoare logic and Kleene algebra with tests. *Trans. Computational Logic* **1**(1), 60–76 (July 2000)
45. Lack, S.: Composing PROPs. *Theory and Application of Categories* **13**(9), 147–163 (2004)
46. Laplaza, M.L.: Coherence for distributivity. In: Kelly, G.M., Laplaza, M., Lewis, G., Mac Lane, S. (eds.) *Coherence in Categories*. pp. 29–65. *Lecture Notes in Mathematics*, Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg (1972). <https://doi.org/10.1007/BFb0059555>
47. Lawvere, F.W.: *Functorial Semantics of Algebraic Theories*. Ph.D. thesis, Columbia University, New York, NY, USA (1963)
48. Mac Lane, S.: *Categories for the Working Mathematician*, *Graduate Texts in Mathematics*, vol. 5. Springer-Verlag, New York, second edn. (1978)
49. Martin, U., Mathiesen, E.A., Oliva, P.: Hoare logic in the abstract. In: *International Workshop on Computer Science Logic*. pp. 501–515. Springer (2006)
50. O’Hearn, P.W.: Incorrectness logic. *Proceedings of the ACM on Programming Languages* **4**(POPL), 1–32 (2019)
51. Piedeleu, R., Zanasi, F.: A Finite Axiomatisation of Finite-State Automata Using String Diagrams. *Logical Methods in Computer Science* **Volume 19, Issue 1** (Feb 2023). [https://doi.org/10.46298/lmcs-19\(1:13\)2023](https://doi.org/10.46298/lmcs-19(1:13)2023)
52. Pous, D.: On the positive calculus of relations with transitive closure. In: Niedermeier, R., Vallée, B. (eds.) *35th Symposium on Theoretical Aspects of Computer Science, STACS 2018*, February 28 to March 3, 2018, Caen, France. *LIPICs*, vol. 96, pp. 3:1–3:16. Schloss Dagstuhl - Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik (2018). <https://doi.org/10.4230/LIPICs.STACS.2018.3>
53. Pratt, V.R.: Semantical considerations on floyd-hoare logic. In: *17th Annual Symposium on Foundations of Computer Science (sfcs 1976)*. pp. 109–121. IEEE (1976)
54. Selinger, P.: A note on Bainbridge’s power set construction. *Ann Arbor* **1001**, 48109–1109 (1998)
55. Selinger, P.: A survey of graphical languages for monoidal categories. In: *New structures for physics*, pp. 289–355. Springer (2010)
56. Stein, D., Staton, S.: Probabilistic programming with exact conditions. *Journal of the ACM* (2023)
57. Winskel, G.: *The formal semantics of programming languages: an introduction*. MIT press (1993)

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